

each of $\cos(-Et+px)\cos(-Et+px)$ which is problematic as there is no medium and furthermore $\cos(-Et+px)$ is not an eigenfunction of the momentum operator $-i\partial/\partial x$. One might argue, however, that a photon solution using E proportional to $\cos(-Et+px)$ and B proportional to $\cos(-Et+px)$ is also not a momentum eigenstate if one uses $-i\partial/\partial x$.

To clarify this, we consider the Dirac equation and the analogous photon equation.

$$\text{Dirac equation: } i\partial/\partial t \psi(x,t) = -i\partial/\partial x \psi(x,t) + m_0 \psi(x,t) \quad ((3))$$

In such a case, one must have a two dimensional $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ because of the rest mass term on the RHS. A similar photon wave equation may be obtained from the Poynting continuity equation: $\partial/\partial t (\mathbf{E}+i\mathbf{B})_i + i \epsilon_{ijk} \partial/\partial x_j (\mathbf{E}+i\mathbf{B})_k = 0$. $\partial/\partial t$ and $\partial/\partial x$ both change $\cos(-Et+px)$ into a sin form, but there is no term to force a second dimension. Thus there is a fundamental difference in the "solution" of a free particle $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ and a photon (or classical wave) $\cos(-Et+px)$.

In (3) we argued this difference is due to the manner in which the energy-momentum disturbance propagates. For a classical wave (string, sound in air, water wave) the disturbance perturbs the medium, but the medium does not travel with it. It is removed and one may focus on a crest e.g. $\cos(-Et+px)$. For light there is no medium, but the E and B fields move like a classical wave.

For a single particle, the real part of $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, namely $\cos(-Et+px)$ has the appearance of a classical wave i.e. the energy-momentum disturbance uses the single particle as its medium. This single particle, however, must travel together with the disturbance and so we argued that one must describe this situation with two dimensions. The first describes the particle as a medium and the second represents the magnitude of its change in $x+dx$. Thus one uses $\cos(px)+i\sin(px)$. The orthogonality ensures that "probability" is conserved as argued in (3).

Dispersion Relationships

It seems $A = -Et+px$ may be linked to dispersion relationships if one uses a second Lorentz invariant:

$$E^2 = p^2c^2 + m_0^2c^4 \quad ((4)) \quad \text{For a photon, } m_0=0.$$

We suggest that for a photon, two dispersion relationships follow:

From ((4)): $E = pc$ so $dE/dv = c dp/dv$ ((5)) where v is the velocity of a frame observing the photon. This result is equivalent to $dA = 0 = -t dE/dv + x dp/dv$. In previous notes, we did not apply this form to a photon, but only to a particle with rest mass. We note that c remains a constant.

A second dispersion relationship for a photon is $dA=0 = -E dt + p dx$ which is equivalent to $E=pc$. As a result, a photon in a lab frame $E(v) = p(v) c$ viewed in a moving frame with velocity v , is described $E = p c$. The speed of the photon remains the same, namely c if it is in a vacuum. This is very different behaviour from a particle with rest mass.

For a particle with rest mass, we do not use $dA=0 = -E dt + p dx$ because one cannot follow a crest as in the classical wave case. There are two dimensions creating the overall motion.

One may use, however, $E^2 = p^2 + m^2 c^2$ together with $dA = 0 = -t dE/dv + x dp/dv$ which was used for a photon and find that $E = mc^2/\sqrt{1-v^2}$ and $p=mv/\sqrt{1-v^2}$ i.e. derive the form of a Lorentz transformation. As a result :

$$P = Ev \quad ((5))$$

This gives the sense of momentum as representing energy flow, but this only holds for a particle with rest mass. $c=E/p$ for a photon which does not represent the same physical scenario, but both a particle with rest mass and a photon have momentum. One may ask: How should momentum be viewed so that it is consistent for both?

Momentum in Terms of Impulses?

Newton's second law states:

$$\Delta p = \int dt \text{ Force}(t) = \text{Impulse} \quad ((6))$$

Thus a change in momentum (i.e. an interaction or measurement) may be considered in terms of an impulse. This should hold for both a photon (striking foil) or a particle with rest mass. Furthermore, we have argued in previous notes that this interpretation allows one to create a statistical picture of a quantum bound state which does not contain acceleration (just as one does not think of a photon in a vacuum as accelerating). One creates a distribution for the particle: $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ and defines $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx)/W(x)$. $V(x)$ is written as $\sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ so it too is defined in terms of impulses. One may then impose conservation of energy at each x point i.e.

$$\{ \sum_p a(p) p^2/2m \exp(ipx) \} / W(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((7)) \text{ Schrodinger time-independent equation.}$$

As a result, an impulse picture to describe momentum seems to apply to both the quantum free particle and a photon.

Conclusion

The quantum free particle and photon seem to be similar in that each may be described by $A=-Et+px$. For the free particle A is the relativistic or nonrelativistic classical action with v written as x/t . For the photon A is a solution of the Poynting continuity equation which follows from Maxwell's EM equations. Furthermore $E^2 = p^2 c^2 + m^2 c^4$ holds for both, with $m=0$ for the photon. One may ask then: What is the difference between the two? If one writes a Dirac equation for the free particle it contains a d/dt partial, d/dx partial and m term. d/dt and d/dx affect $\text{function}(-Et+px)$ in a similar way in that they convert it to $d \text{ function}(y)/dy$, but the m term

does not. Thus one is forced to introduce two dimensions i.e. $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. Alternatively, a solution of the Klein-Gordon equation which is at the same time an eigenfunction of momentum must also be two dimensional.

One may write a photon wave equation from the Poynting continuity equation which is of the same form as the Dirac equation, but with $Ei+iB$ (Ei =electric field, B magnetic) as the wavefunction and $eijk$ (Levi-Civita symbol) as the spin matrix. The difference is that there is no m term and so $\cos(-Et+px)$ is sufficient for both Ei and B . In other words there is only one dimension. In (3) we argued that a particle must be represented by two dimensions because one describes the disturbance of a single particle medium $\cos(-Et+px)$ due to the energy-momentum wave and the other the change in this medium which follows from the particle following the disturbance (unlike a classical medium).

We argue that using $EE = pp + momo$ and $A = -Et+px$ leads to dispersion relationships. For a photon $m_0=0$ so $E=pc$, but this also follows from $dA = 0 = -E dt + p dx$. Furthermore one may apply $dA=0 = -t dE/dv + x dp/dv$ because $E=pc$. $E=pc$ suggests that the photon has the same velocity regardless of which moving frame observes it.

For a particle, we rule out $dA = -E dt + p dx$ because the motion is not due to a simple translation of dx and dt as in the $\cos(-Et+px)$ case. As a result, one uses $EE = pp + momo$ together with $dA=0 = -t dE/dv + x dp/dv$ to derive the Lorentz form $p=Ev$ with $E=m_0/\sqrt{1-v^2}$.

As a result, a photon and free particle have different dispersion relationships, but they both have momentum. It is only for the particle that one has the picture of energy flow i.e. $p=Ev$. We thus suggest that momentum be thought of in terms of impulse as in the case of Newton's second law: $dp = \text{Force}(t) dt$. This idea may be applied to a bound state by considering $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k V_k \exp(ikx)$ and using a distribution of free particles $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)$.

References

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